

ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ДАВЛАТ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРАСИНИ РАҚАМЛАШТИРИШ ЖАРАЁНИНИНГ ТАХЛИЛИ

АНАЛИЗ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

ANALYSIS OF DIGITALIZATION OF PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

**Rakhmatova N.A., PhD,
National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek**

**Nurmuhammadov L.O., 4th year student, Economics faculty,
National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek**

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада «рақамли иқтисодиёт» иқтисодий категорияси ўрганилади ва Ўзбекистоннинг иқтисодиётни рақамлаштириш жараёнидаги ҳозирги ҳолати таққослаб анализ қилинади. Мақолада шунингдек, мамлакатнинг давлат инфраструктурасининг рақамли трансформациясининг асосий жиҳатлари, жумладан, стратегиялар ва концепцияларни ишлаб чиқиш ва жорий этиш, телекоммуникацион инфраструктурани ривожлантириш ва яхшилаш, қўшимча марказлар ва электрон платформалар яратишга инвестициялар киритиш каби ҳукуматнинг саъй-ҳаракатлари кўриб чиқилади.

Калит сўзлар: рақамли иқтисодиёт, рақамли трансформация, ахборот технологиялари, иқтисодий ўсиш, давлат инфраструктураси.

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется экономическая категория «цифровая экономика» и проведен сравнительный анализ текущего положения Узбекистана в процессе цифровизации экономики. В статье также рассматриваются ключевые аспекты цифровой трансформации государственной инфраструктуры страны, включая усилия правительства в виде разработки и внедрении стратегий и концепций, развитие и улучшение телекоммуникационной инфраструктуры, инвестиции в создание дополнительных центров и электронных платформ.

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, цифровая трансформация, информационные технологии, экономический рост, государственная инфраструктура translate into english

Abstract. This article examines the economic category of the «digital economy» and conducts a comparative analysis of Uzbekistan's current position in the process of

digitalizing the economy. The article also explores key aspects of the digital transformation of the country's public infrastructure, including government efforts in the form of developing and implementing strategies and concepts, developing and improving telecommunications infrastructure, and investing in the creation of additional centres and electronic platforms.

Keywords: digital economy, digital transformation, information technology, economic growth, public infrastructure

Introduction

Digitalization is a powerful force shaping today's economy and society, with profound implications for economic expansion, labour market dynamics, wage patterns, and consumer welfare, leading to transformative changes in society and the economy. The global trend towards digital public infrastructure has become an integral part of the broader digital transformation that is occurring across all sectors of the economy. This shift toward digitalized public infrastructure is revolutionizing urban and national service management and delivery. Accelerated by the swift progress in technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), big data analytics, cloud computing, and blockchain, this movement is gaining recognition from governments globally for its ability to improve public service in terms of efficiency, reach, and quality¹. Digitalization in Uzbekistan is part of the country's broader initiative to modernize and enhance its economy and public services through the adoption of digital technologies. The government of Uzbekistan has been actively pursuing policies and projects aimed at fostering a digital transformation across various sectors. For instance, the «Digital Uzbekistan 2030» strategy is a comprehensive plan set forth by the government of Uzbekistan (Presidential Decree №6079, which is effective from 2020) to drive the country's digital transformation until 2030. The strategy aims to create a digital economy and society by leveraging advanced technologies, to enhance economic growth and improve public services through the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in all sectors and areas, primarily in public administration, education, healthcare, and agriculture². Another significant strategy is «UZBEKISTAN – 2030» (Presidential Decree №178, which is effective from 2023) in which Uzbekistan's digital transformation strategy aims: to provide nationwide internet access and enhance digital connectivity; to improve the country's digital governance and elevate its position in international e-government rankings; to expand IT sector, attracting foreign investment, and fostering innovation with the development of significant startup ventures and others. Moreover, Presidential

¹ United Nations., (2018). «E-Government Survey 2018: Gearing E-Government to Support Transformation Towards Sustainable and Resilient Societies». United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (URL: <https://publicadministration.un.org/egovkb/en-us/Reports/UN-E-Government-Survey-2018>)

² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, PD №6079, 2020., «On approval of the strategy “DIGITAL UZBEKISTAN-2030” and measures for its effective implementation» (URL: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5031048#>)

Decrees №3832 «On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan» and №4022 «On measures for further modernization of digital infrastructure to develop the digital economy» also support the intentions of the government on enhancing digital aspects of the economy. The main purpose of the article is to analyze the digitalization condition of Uzbekistan's public infrastructure, implemented projects and their impact on the socio-economic well-being of the country.

Literature review

Digital transformation has become a critical focus for governments worldwide. The theoretical underpinnings of digitalization are explored by Dedola, L., Ehrmann, M., Hoffmann, P., Lamo, A., Paz Pardo, G., Slacalek, J., Strasser, G. (2023)³, who provide a foundational understanding of digital transformation and its relevance to public infrastructure. Moreover, Brynjolfsson, E., and Kahin, B. (2003)⁴ were one of the early scientists, who characterized the digital economy as one that is driven by the conversion of information into a digital format, emphasizing the shift towards a digital-centric economy and highlighting its critical role in fostering continued economic expansion.

Researchers such as Matthias Finger and Juan Montero (2022)⁵ explored the impact of digitalization on infrastructure and infrastructure-based public services, introducing digitalization as a significant layer above foundational infrastructure and services provided by the government. Similarly, other studies by authors such as Nochta, T., Wan, L., Schooling, J. M., Lemanski, C., Parlikad, A. K., & Jin, Y. (2019)⁶, Lippert, I. (2022)⁷, Paul, M., Upadhyay, P., & Dwivedi, Y. K. (2020)⁸ collectively demonstrate the strategic approaches and sectoral advancements, highlights the transformative impact of digital technologies on urban planning that are driving the digitalization of public infrastructure.

Methodology

In the article, the authors employed mixed methods to investigate the economic impact of digitalization on public infrastructure. The research design integrates both

³ Dedola, Luca and Ehrmann, Michael and Hoffmann, Peter and Lamo, Ana and Paz-Pardo, Gonzalo and Slacalek, Jiri and Strasser, Georg H., (April 2023). Digitalisation and the Economy., ECB Working Paper No. 2023/2809, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4429773> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4429773>

⁴ Brynjolfsson, E., & Kahin, B. (2003). Understanding the digital economy: data, tools, and research. *Journal of Documentation*, 59(4), 487-490. (DOI: [10.1108/00220410310485785](https://doi.org/10.1108/00220410310485785))

⁵ Finger, M., & Montero, J. (2022). The digitalisation of infrastructure and infrastructure-based (public) services: what are the problems? *Network Industries Quarterly*, 24, 1 (URL: <https://www.network-industries.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/The-digitalisation-of-infrastructure-and-infrastructure-based-public-services-what-are-the-problems.pdf>)

⁶ Nochta, T., Wan, L., Schooling, J. M., Lemanski, C., Parlikad, A. K., & Jin, Y. (2019). Digitalisation for smarter cities: moving from a static to a dynamic view. *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers-Smart Infrastructure and Construction*, 171(4), 117-130 (URL: <https://doi.org/10.1680/jsmic.19.00001>)

⁷ Lippert, I. (2022). Digitalisation as promissory infrastructure for sustainability. In *Handbook of Critical Environmental Politics* (pp. 540-553). Edward Elgar Publishing (URL: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781839100673.00049>)

⁸ Paul, M., Upadhyay, P., & Dwivedi, Y. K. (2020). Roadmap to digitalisation of an emerging economy: a viewpoint. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 14(3), 401-415 (URL: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/TG-03-2020-0054/full/html>)

quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive analysis of the effects of digitalization on economic growth and efficiency in public services. Moreover, the general economic methods of searching and systematizing theoretical data, induction and deduction analysis were also applied.

Results

Digitalization of the economy is a term often referred to as digital transformation of the economy, which is integrating digital technology into all areas of a business or economy, fundamentally changing how companies run and deliver value to customers. Digitalization of public infrastructure refers to integrating digital technologies into the systems and services that are essential for the functioning of a society⁹. The aim is to set up integrated and smart networks that enhance the provision of services and the administration of resources in diverse domains such as transport, energy, water, sanitation, and civil protection. A range of indicators is used to evaluate the expansion of digitalization into the public infrastructure, which is related to the development level of its information and communication technologies. On the one hand, international indexes such as World Bank's GovTech Maturity, UN's E-Government Development and Government Artificial Intelligence Readiness by Oxford Insights will be in use to see the results of implementations of digital projects in the economy in worldwide scope. On the other hand, national statistical information will be insightful to analyze the current conditions of public infrastructure digitalization.

Uzbekistan's progress in digital reforms is clear in its upward trajectory in various global digitalization indices. For instance, Uzbekistan has climbed to the list of leaders among such developed countries as Sweden, Germany, France, Norway, Japan, and others in the GovTech Maturity Index for public services in 2022¹⁰. The GovTech Maturity Index is a benchmarking tool designed to assess and compare the level of technology integration and digitalization within government services across different countries. The index typically considers factors such as the availability and quality of online government services, the use of digital tools to engage with citizens, the implementation of e-government strategies, and the infrastructure supporting digital government initiatives. In the 2022 E-Government Development Index (EGDI), which is part of the UN e-government survey, Uzbekistan ranked 66th position out of the 192 countries assessed with 0.7265/1. This ranking reflects the country's standing in terms of its e-government capabilities and the maturity of its digital public services, which are measured based on the composition of the Online Service Index (OSI), Telecommunication Infrastructure Index (TII) and Human

⁹ Schwab Klaus.,14 Jan (2016). World Economic Forum, «The Fourth Industrial Revolution: what it means, how to respond» (URL: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2016/01/the-fourth-industrial-revolution-what-it-means-and-how-to-respond/>)

¹⁰ World Bank, 2022. «WBG GovTech Maturity Index 2022 Update: Trends in Public Sector Digital Transformation» (URL: sw-1688459611-World Bank GMTI 2023 REPORT_230326_183857_230704_112408.pdf (ega.go.tz))

Capital Index (HCI)¹¹. It shows that the country is above the median and has made considerable progress in developing its e-government services and digital infrastructure. Furthermore, according to the Government Artificial Intelligence Readiness Index by Oxford Insights, Uzbekistan in 2023 was among the top ten in the South and Central Asian countries with 43.79. This index measures a country's ability to implement AI technologies in the public sector, considering factors such as governance, infrastructure, data availability, and education and talent. This ranking in this index implies that Uzbekistan is well-positioned to use AI for improving public service delivery, policymaking, and addressing social challenges.

Now, it will be expedient to analyze the current state of public digitalization based on the statistical information of the Uzbek Statistics Agency. Through analysis of statistical data for the information and e-commerce sector from 2016 to 2022, we can conclude that indicators, gross value added created in the sector of the information economy and e-commerce and its share, absolute in trillions of soums and as a percentage of GDP, demonstrate an upward trend. For instance, in 2016, this indicator in absolute terms was approximately 5 trillion soums, whereas by 2022, there is a marked increase of more than fivefold. Since during the 2016-2022 period under study Uzbekistan's GDP also exhibited a growth trend, it would be significant to investigate the share this sector occupies in the total GDP of the country and how this indicator has changed. The share of the information economy and digital commerce in the country's GDP increased from 2.1% in 2016 to 3.4% in 2022, which represents an increase of 1.6 times. The volume of services in the information and communication sector increased sixfold from 2016 to 2022¹². The country's telecommunications infrastructure has also exhibited significant growth: the length of fibre-optic lines has increased by 7.7 times, from 22.1 thousand kilometres in 2016 to 170.6 thousand kilometres in 2022, and the number of mobile base stations has risen by 1.1 times, from 45,900 to 53,600 units, relative to the previous year¹³. These indicators prove the intensive expansion from 2016 to 2022 in coverage and provision of accessible communication and internet to an even greater portion of the population.

As of October 1, 2022, the number of subscribers with mobile connectivity reached 30.9 million. Consequently, mobile coverage is provided for every 75 out of 100 individuals in the country. The number of internet users has increased by 1.1 times relative to the year 2021, reaching 26.7 million people in 2022. Internet service tariffs have been gradually exhibiting a downward trend. Moreover, the National Statistics Agency reports¹⁴ that over the past five years, the telecommunications and information technology sector has seen a growth of 1.8 times in the number of companies. As of early 2023, the country boasts more than 12,000 ICT firms. The

¹¹ COUNTRY RATINGS, Infrastructure: E-Government Development Index for Uzbekistan (URL: <https://stat.uz/en/official-statistics/tsifrovaya-ekonomika-eng>).

¹² Source: Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Open Data, Digital Economy.

¹³ Source: Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Open Data, Digital Economy.

¹⁴ Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Open Data, Digital Economy (URL: <https://stat.uz/en/official-statistics/tsifrovaya-ekonomika-eng>).

industry supplies jobs for over 100,000 individuals. By the close of 2022, the ICT service sector saw a surge of 125.5% in volume, reaching a total of 22.9 trillion soums, with programming services contributed by local companies and experts accounting for 4.2 trillion soums of this figure. In the first quarter of 2023, the IT sector's total income soared to 2.38 trillion soums, nearly quadrupling the revenue from the corresponding period in the previous year. The export of digital services also saw an increase, hitting \$57.2 million. IT Park showed that the net income represented over 90% of the sector's revenue, equating to 2.158 trillion soums. It is important to mention the key entities and platforms, which were created with the goal of economic digitalization. The first one is the Digital Government project management centre, which was created under the Ministry of digital technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan to implement the main directions of reforms in the field of the digital economy and the improvement of the «Digital government» system as part of the development of the «Digital Uzbekistan-2030» strategy. Nowadays, this centre coordinates 2000 high-priority state projects, provides 56% of all public services and implements 606 public services through/in the interactive public services portal (the unified portal of interactive public services)¹⁵. The Unified Portal of Interactive Public Services of Uzbekistan, known as «my.gov.uz», is an online platform that streamlines access to a variety of government services for citizens, businesses, and foreigners. It aims to enhance the efficiency and transparency of public administration by offering services such as personal document management, business registration, tax filing, visa applications, and utility payments. The portal also provides information about government agencies and their services¹⁶.

Conclusion

Digitalization is pivotal to Uzbekistan's advancement, driving economic diversification, enhancing the efficiency and transparency of government services, and bolstering global competitiveness. It plays a crucial role in developing a skilled workforce through digital education, improving healthcare delivery, and fostering social inclusion by bridging the digital divide. Additionally, digitalization supports sustainable development, spurs innovation, and underpins critical infrastructure enhancements. Ultimately, it contributes to elevating the quality of life for Uzbekistan's citizens, positioning the nation for sustainable, long-term progress in an increasingly digital world.

References:

1. Brynjolfsson, E., & Kahin, B. (2003). Understanding the digital economy: data, tools, and research. *Journal of Documentation*, 59(4), 487-490. (DOI: [10.1108/00220410310485785](https://doi.org/10.1108/00220410310485785))

¹⁵ Digital Government project management center's official website (URL: <https://e-gov.uz/en/about>)

¹⁶ The Unified Portal of Interactive Public Services of Uzbekistan's official website (URL: <https://my.gov.uz/>)

2. COUNTRY RATINGS, Infrastructure: E-Government Development Index for Uzbekistan (URL: <https://countryrank.org/cat-infrastructure/rating-e-government-development-index/uzbekistan.html>).
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, PD №6079, 2020., «On approval of the strategy “DIGITAL UZBEKISTAN-2030” and measures for its effective implementation» (URL: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5031048#>)
4. Dedola, Luca and Ehrmann, Michael and Hoffmann, Peter and Lamo, Ana and Paz-Pardo, Gonzalo and Slacalek, Jiri and Strasser, Georg H., (April 2023). Digitalisation and the Economy., ECB Working Paper No. 2023/2809, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4429773> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4429773>
5. Digital Government project management center’s official website (URL: <https://e-gov.uz/en/about>).
6. Finger, M., & Montero, J. (2022). The digitalisation of infrastructure and infrastructure-based (public) services: what are the problems? Network Industries Quarterly, 24, 1 (URL: <https://www.network-industries.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/The-digitalisation-of-infrastructure-and-infrastructure-based-public-services-what-are-the-problems.pdf>)
7. Lippert, I. (2022). Digitalisation as promissory infrastructure for sustainability. In Handbook of Critical Environmental Politics (pp. 540-553). Edward Elgar Publishing (URL: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781839100673.00049>)
8. Nochta, T., Wan, L., Schooling, J. M., Lemanski, C., Parlikad, A. K., & Jin, Y. (2019). Digitalisation for smarter cities: moving from a static to a dynamic view. Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers-Smart Infrastructure and Construction, 171(4), 117-130 (URL: <https://doi.org/10.1680/jsmic.19.00001>)
9. Paul, M., Upadhyay, P., & Dwivedi, Y. K. (2020). Roadmap to digitalisation of an emerging economy: a viewpoint. Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy, 14(3), 401-415 (URL: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/TG-03-2020-0054/full/html>)
10. Schwab Klaus., 14 Jan (2016). World Economic Forum, «The Fourth Industrial Revolution: what it means, how to respond» (URL: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2016/01/the-fourth-industrial-revolution-what-it-means-and-how-to-respond/>)
11. Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Open Data, Digital Economy (URL: <https://stat.uz/en/official-statistics/tsifrovaya-ekonomika-eng>).
12. The Unified Portal of Interactive Public Services of Uzbekistan’s official website (URL: <https://my.gov.uz/>).
13. United Nations., (2018). «E-Government Survey 2018: Gearing E-Government to Support Transformation Towards Sustainable and Resilient Societies». United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (URL: <https://publicadministration.un.org/egovkb/en-us/Reports/UN-E-Government-Survey-2018>)

14. World Bank, 2022. «WBG GovTech Maturity Index 2022 Update: Trends in Public Sector Digital Transformation» (URL: [sw-1688459611-World Bank GMTI 2023 REPORT_230326_183857_230704_112408.pdf](https://ega.go.tz/sw-1688459611-World%20Bank%20GMTI%202023%20REPORT_230326_183857_230704_112408.pdf) (ega.go.tz)).